

**DETECTION AND MONITORING OF PSYLLID VECTORS OF *CANDIDATUS*
LIBERIBACTER SOLANACEARUM IN SCOTLAND**

**LITERATURE REVIEW: SAMPLING METHODS FOR THE DETECTION AND MONITORING
OF PSYLLID VECTORS AND THE PATHOGEN *CALSOL***

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I OVERVIEW AND AIMS

The proteobacterium 'Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum' (CaLsol) is an emerging threat to a range of crops most notably potato, tomato, carrot and celery. CaLsol causes zebra chip symptoms in potatoes in the Americas and New Zealand, reducing tuber yield and processing quality (Butler and Trumble 2012). Although it has not been recorded in the UK, CaLsol has been reported in several areas of Europe including Scandinavia, France, Spain and the Canary Islands.

CaLsol was initially recorded in Mexico in 1994 infecting potato. From there it has spread through much of Central and Northern America and also to New Zealand where it is thought a psyllid vector was accidentally introduced into tomato crops grown under glass. Escape of the psyllid allowed it to transfer infection to potato, and losses of up to 16% of total yield are now being reported (mainly due to unmarketable tubers). The vector associated with spread in the Americas and New Zealand is *Bactericera cockerelli*. This psyllid species is not native to the UK or Europe, however two additional psyllid species *Trioza apicalis* (Munyaneza et al., 2010) and *Bactericera trigonica* (Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2012), are believed to be responsible for spread in Europe, with a further two (*B. tremblayi* and *B. nigricornis*) currently under investigation. *Trioza apicalis* has been recorded in southern England, but it is not clear how widespread it is, or if *B. trigonica* is present in the UK. As several species of psyllid have already been implicated as vectors of this disease, it is possible that if any of the UK's native psyllids feed on potato and/or carrot, they may be capable of spreading the disease. Potential spread of this disease into Scotland is of great concern to both carrot and potato growers as researchers in Spain have experimentally transmitted CaLsol from carrot to potato using a psyllid vector.

I.1 MONITORING AIMS

This report provides a number of recommendations in order to mitigate the risk of the introduction and subsequent spread of the inoculum, CaLsol. The primary objective will be to specifically limit the risk of infection to potato crops. More generally, as a secondary objective, these strategies should also aim to limit the risk of CaLsol infection of other hosts, including both crops and non-crop species. Consequently, we consider four possible monitoring scenarios.

- 1) Monitor for the detection of a CaLsol epidemic outbreak,
 - a) Specifically within potato crops.
 - b) Within any non-potato host (crop or non-crop) within Scotland.
- 2) Monitor for the intervention and containment of a CaLsol epidemic, given an outbreak has occurred,
 - a) Specifically within potato crops.
 - b) Within any non-potato host (crop or non-crop) within Scotland.

I.1.1 POTENTIAL MONITORING PROGRAMS

Monitoring strategies typically depend upon sampling key markers to provide a representative view of the population status at particular time points. Consequently, in order to implement an effective monitoring strategy, one needs to identify both the markers that should be sampled and additionally the associated sampling method that will yield the most efficient data collection procedure. In the following recommendations, we address both of these issues based on the current knowledge of the risk of CaLsol to the Scottish potato industry.

As detailed in the review by Sjölund et al. (2015) the main pathways for the introduction and spread of CaLsol are:

1. The importation of infected hosts

2. The infection of established host plants
3. The importation of psyllids that are competent vectors of CaLsol.
4. The migration of competent psyllid vectors
5. Established psyllids becoming competent vectors of CaLsol.

Note that a competent vector refers to a psyllid species that is able to transmit CaLsol to a host species. More specifically, we will refer to a competent vector to potato crops as a psyllid species that is specifically able to transmit CaLsol to potato crops. For instance, the psyllid *T. apicalis* primarily hosts on carrot plants and if it is able to additionally host on potato plants, *T. apicalis* would then be considered a competent vector for potatoes. It has been suggested that psyllids have a high capacity to evolve in such a way as to leap to new plant species (Haapalainen, 2014).

Consequently, initial monitoring and early warning sampling schemes should target these main pathways. In particular, we have identified the following list of potential monitoring programs.

- Sample imported potatoes for CaLsol.
- Sample other imported hosts for CaLsol.
- Sample established potato crops for CaLsol.
- Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for CaLsol.
- Sample imported potatoes for competent psyllid vectors.
- Sample other imported hosts for competent psyllid vectors.
- Sample established potato crops for competent psyllid vectors.
- Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for competent psyllid vectors.
- Sample for migrating competent psyllid vectors.
- Sample for CaLsol in psyllid vectors.
- Sample for the evolution of established psyllids to become competent vectors to potato crops.

Clearly, it is not feasible to monitor all possible pathways and the trade-off between the cost and benefit of the different monitoring schemes should be assessed. Moreover, the benefit of each scheme will depend on the specific scenario of interest. For example, the priority of the above sampling schemes will differ if one is intending to monitor for CaLsol infection before an initial outbreak, compared to a monitoring strategy after CaLsol infection has been confirmed in Scotland. Thus the following recommendations assess the cost and benefit of each monitoring scheme under these different scenarios.

II RECOMMENDATIONS

Our recommendations consist of prioritising the list of possible monitoring programs for each of the four scenarios of interest and to also identify associated sampling strategies. The specific design of any sampling strategy depends on a number of different factors and we provide, as part of the project output, the following review (in Sections 1-4) into the statistical and mathematical approaches to the design of efficient sampling strategies.

II.I MONITORING FOR DETECTION

In the scenario where the main aim of any monitoring scheme is to monitor before CaLsol has been detected in Scotland, any monitoring scheme should be assessed by the criteria to either substantially increase the chance of detecting CaLsol or to dramatically reduce the risk of a high impact epidemic. The risk/benefit analysis associated with this scenario is summarised in Table 1 below;

TABLE 1: RISK/BENEFIT ANALYSIS FOR DIFFERENT MONITING SCHEMES BEFORE THE DETECTION OF A CALSOL OUTBREAK

Monitoring scheme (before CaLsol detection)	Level of benefit associated with primary objective – <i>mitigate risk of CaLsol infection to potato crops</i>	Level of benefit associated with secondary objective – <i>mitigate risk of CaLsol infection to other host species</i>
Sample imported potatoes for CaLsol.	High. Decrease risk of a high impact epidemic.	Low. Current restrictions on potato imports reduce the likelihood of CaLsol introduction.
Sample other imported hosts for CaLsol.	Low. Decrease risk of an epidemic but since there is currently no identified competent vector to potato in Scotland, the risk of transmission to potato crops would be low.	Medium. Decrease risk of outbreak in non-potato hosts.
Sample established potato crops for CaLsol.	High. Increase potential to identify initiation of an epidemic and also provides evidence for the existence of a competent vector to potato crops in Scotland.	Medium. Decrease risk of spreading the infection to other hosts.
Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for CaLsol.	Low. Even if these samples tested positive, there is currently little risk to potato crop if CaLsol is present in other species without the additional presence of a competent vector to potato crops.	Medium. Although trialled in 2012–2013 where growers were asked to send samples of infected carrot crops to SASA, of the 5 identified samples, none tested positive for CaLsol.
Sample imported potatoes for competent psyllid vectors.	Medium-High. Decrease risk of a high impact epidemic, but unlikely to be fruitful since there are already limitations on the source of potato imports (Sjölund et al., 2015).	Medium. Current restrictions on potato imports reduce the likelihood of competent vector introduction.
Sample other imported hosts for competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Decrease risk of a high impact epidemic in potatoes, but unlikely to be fruitful.	High. Decrease risk of epidemic in non-potato hosts.
Sample established potato crops for competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Decrease risk of a high impact epidemic but currently, there is no evidence of a competent vector to potato crops in Scotland.	Medium. Decrease risk of an undetected epidemic.
Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for competent psyllid vectors.	Low. Currently, no evidence of a competent vector to potato crops in Scotland.	High. Provides information regarding the distribution of potential vectors (for any hosts) of CaLsol.
Sample for migrating competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Increase probability of detecting initial epidemics.	Medium. Increase probability of detecting initial epidemics.
Sample for CaLsol in psyllid vectors.	Medium. No evidence the psyllid vector is competent at transmission to potatoes.	High. Increase probability of detecting initial epidemics.
Sample for the evolution of established psyllids to become competent vectors to potato crops.	Low. Although this would be beneficial to reduce the risk of a CaLsol epidemic in potatoes, it will be hard to ascertain this information.	N/A

As detailed in Sjölund et al. (2015), imported potatoes have been routinely tested for CaLsol infection since 2010. In order to further reduce the risk of a CaLsol epidemic spreading undetected, we would also recommend the implementation of a scheme to monitor potato crops already established within Scotland and as an additional precaution to also monitor for the existence of competent and infected vectors of CaLsol. One output from this project will be the development of a molecular assay to identify potential psyllid vectors of

CaLsol. Thus, future monitoring of CaLsol can be achieved through the routine testing of identified psyllid vectors. In order to implement these additional monitoring schemes, we recommend the sampling procedures described below.

Sample established potato crops for CaLsol infection

Samples of potato crops should be taken randomly in both space and time in order to obtain a representative sample of the crop. Since CaLsol will be (initially) a rare occurrence within potatoes, the sampling scheme may be improved in terms of cost effectiveness through disproportionate stratification and composite sampling (see Section 2.2 for details). For example, the potato crop landscape may be stratified according to informative characteristics, to be determined based on the review by Sjölund et al. (2015), such that some strata are more at risk of CaLsol infection than others.

Sample for the arrival of competent vectors

Since the aim of this monitoring scheme is to detect the presence of competent psyllid vectors, it becomes more efficient to purposively sample where the psyllids of interest are likely to be present. Consequently, for migrating competent vectors the locations to sample in order to increase the probability of detection will be at the points of invasion. Thus, field traps (sticky or water traps) could be placed at locations identified as high risk invasion points such as import hotspots and also the boundaries of any migratory dynamics. For example, *B. tremblayi*, found in France, will most likely only enter Scotland through the southern border and consequently, the placement of traps should be along this boundary.

However, the cost of such field sampling may not be outweighed by the benefits. An alternative would be to routinely monitor psyllid species within the existing suction trap network. There may be limitations to the reliance of suction trap data and it is an output from the current project to correlate the efficiency of suction traps to field data for psyllids, as has previously been done for aphids (Fabre et al., 2010). Thus if limitations are identified, this will then identify prime locations for additional field traps that the suction traps cannot efficiently sample. In addition, although suction traps are known to sample with relatively high efficiency for both types of dispersal behaviour in aphids (short range summer dispersal and long range winter migration) this has yet to be corroborated for psyllids and may also identify the need to focus field sampling in summer where psyllid dispersal patterns are over smaller distances. The most important feature of this monitoring scheme is that if a competent vector is found, it should then become routine to test for CaLsol within the identified competent vectors as this will provide information of likely epidemic source points.

II.II MONITORING FOR INTERVENTION

The above assessment is suited to monitoring **before** an outbreak of CaLsol is detected. Should CaLsol be detected in Scotland, we also consider the steps required to monitor the disease progression in order to design an effective intervention program. An assessment of the different monitoring programs in this scenario is presented in Table 2 below.

TABLE 2: RISK/BENEFIT ANALYSIS FOR DIFFERENT MONITING SCHEMES AFTER DETECTION OF A CALSOL OUTBREAK

Monitoring scheme (after CaLsol detection)	Level of benefit associated with primary objective – <i>mitigate risk of CaLsol infection to potato crops</i>	Level of benefit associated with secondary objective – <i>mitigate risk of CaLsol infection to other host species</i>
Sample imported potatoes for CaLsol.	Medium. Prevent further spread.	Medium. Prevent further spread.
Sample other imported hosts for CaLsol.	Medium. Prevent further spread.	Medium. Prevent further spread.
Sample established potato crops for CaLsol.	High. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic. Also provide	Medium. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic between

	information regarding the effectiveness of any intervention mechanism.	different host species.
Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for CaLsol.	Medium. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic between different host species.	High. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic. Also provide information regarding the effectiveness of any intervention mechanism.
Sample imported potatoes for competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Prevent further spread.	Medium. Prevent further spread.
Sample other imported hosts for competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Prevent further spread.	Medium. Prevent further spread.
Sample established potato crops for competent psyllid vectors.	High. Provides information regarding the likely vector of the inoculum. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic. Also provide information regarding the effectiveness of any intervention mechanism.	High. Provides information regarding the likely vector of the inoculum and consequently identifies any other hosts at risk of infection, such as carrots.
Sample established hosts (excl. potatoes) for competent psyllid vectors.	High. Provides information of the dispersal and host landscape of the likely vectors and consequently, the dispersal of the epidemic.	High. Provide information regarding the spread and dispersal of the epidemic.
Sample for migrating competent psyllid vectors.	Medium. Provide information regarding likely source of outbreaks.	Medium. Provide information regarding likely source of outbreaks.
Sample for CaLsol in psyllid vectors.	High. Provides information regarding the likely vector of the inoculum.	High. Provides information regarding the likely vector of the inoculum.

It is therefore clear that if an outbreak of CaLsol occurs, monitoring schemes should increase in order to assess the spread and dispersal of the epidemic and associated vectors in order to focus intervention policies.

Focussing our attention to the primary objective, identification of a CaLsol epidemic (affecting potato) could occur in one of two ways:

1. Discovery of CaLsol in a potato sample
2. Discovery of CaLsol in an identified competent vector

Upon discovery of the existence of CaLsol infection in potato crops, the main focus of any monitoring scheme should shift to monitoring the extent and spread of the epidemic. If the discovery of CaLsol first occurs in a potato sample, the initial step would be to identify which psyllid species was transmitting the disease. This information might be readily available, but if not one would have to sample for the psyllid vector at the known epidemic locations. Since the aim of this sampling exercise would be to detect with little knowledge of the psyllid density, the most appropriate sampling designs would be to either systematically sample within the host (potato) landscape or to systematically sample along the edge of potato fields, due to the preferential location of psyllids to field edges (Sjölund et al., 2015).

FIGURE 1: DEPICTION OF THE MODELLING PROCESS

Given initial data, a model can be developed to describe the processes of interest, such as psyllid dynamics or CaLsol epidemic dynamics. Additional data can then be obtained to improve the accuracy of the model, for example data samples may be obtained in previously unsampled habitats. Given a model, predictions of the variable of interest, such as the risk of CaLsol infection, or psyllid density can be produced. Again, data samples can be obtained in order to improve the precision of the predictions. Based on these predictions, a targeted intervention can be applied after which a monitoring scheme should be put in place.

Once the transmitting vector had been identified, the focus would be to target intervention methods and to monitor the progression of the epidemic. This would be best achieved through the development of a mechanistic model of either the epidemic or the epidemic risk as described in Section 3.1.2. In general, any project aimed at monitoring the progression and intervention of CaLsol epidemics in Scotland would consist of the following steps as depicted in Figure 1.

1. Obtain initial data in order to estimate certain characteristics of the epidemic. For instance, a key feature to estimate would be the dispersal characteristics of the disease. One way in which data can be obtained to gather this information is through geostatistical approaches (Henne et al., 2012). In particular, one should sample both established hosts and psyllids to ascertain the extent of the disease.
2. Construct a model of the epidemic progression. This could be a mechanistic model describing the interactions between the host, pathogen and vector which would require substantial knowledge of the underlying mechanisms. An alternative to this approach would be to develop a model of the risk landscape of the epidemic as has been demonstrated for sudden oak death either through epidemic modelling (Demon et al., 2011) or to model the risk itself (Parnell et al., 2014). These methods, developed at RRes, give specific attention to monitoring epidemics in the presence of an intervention policy.
3. Once a model has been finalised, predictions can be made about the variable of interest. For example, given a model of the risk of a high-impact epidemic, one can obtain a map of the predicted risk.
4. The subsequent model predictions will likely identify locations to apply an intervention program, such as focussed monitoring at high-risk locations or even pre-emptive interventions in these high-risk areas.
5. Once interventions have taken place, it might then be of interest to develop a further monitoring program for the detection of future CaLsol outbreaks. This would be of a different form to the

monitoring schemes before an outbreak took place, since one would know that competent vectors were already present, and risk-based monitoring programs would be more beneficial.

RRes is strategically and academically well placed to develop modelling strategies of psyllid vectored CaLsol epidemics with our partners SASA, should this arise in the future as referenced above.

III ASPECTS OF THE SAMPLING LITERATURE

We have provided a number of different recommendations in order to effectively monitor both for the detection of an initial CaLsol outbreak and also to effectively monitor the progression of CaLsol epidemics should an outbreak occur. Associated with these monitoring recommendations are the statistical and mathematical approaches to designing the practical sampling schemes that make the most efficient use of sampling resources. For example, the sampling design will dictate how many samples should be taken and also where they should be placed in order to make best use of resources. Although the overall strategy for monitoring and detecting the presence of CaLsol in psyllid vectors is relatively straightforward, the design and implementation of specific sampling regimens can become quite complex. Consequently, the remainder of this review aims to cover the literature regarding different sampling approaches and to provide the necessary background to design the most appropriate sampling scheme for different scenarios, the most relevant of which are summarised in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF SELECTED SAMPLING METHODS

Sampling Method	Description	Potential Usage	Auxiliary Data Required	Limitations	Design Cost	(Potential ¹) Practical Cost
<i>Methods for Estimation of Population Characteristics</i>						
Simple random sample	Each unit has equal probability of being sampled.	Estimation of: - Psyllid density - Psyllid abundance - CaLsol infection within crops - CaLsol infection within psyllids - Presence of vectors - Presence of infection - Etc.			Low	High, likely to need large number of sampling points.
Systematic sampling	Take samples at regularly spaced intervals.			No underlying periodicity in the population characteristic.	Low	High, likely to need large number of sampling points.
Stratified systematic	Take samples at regularly spaced intervals (at different frequencies) within strata.		Strata information.	No periodicity within each stratum.	Low - Medium	Low (if strata knowledge is correct).
Stratified random sampling	Take a random sample within each defined strata.		Strata information.	Between strata variability higher than within strata variability.	Low - Medium	Potentially low (if strata definitions are near optimal).
Adaptive two-stage sequential	A two stage sampling scheme, where the number of secondary units sampled within each primary depends on the outcome of the primary samples.		Require a defined sampling scheme for primary units as well as a criterion for the continuation of sampling.	Particularly beneficial for rare clustered populations.	Medium – High (in order to gain most efficiency)	Low (depending on efficiency of design).
Double sampling/two-phase sampling	Sample an auxiliary variable on a large number of units, then sample the variable of interest on a subset.		An auxiliary variable, correlated to variable of interest.	Design efficiency depends on how well the auxiliary variable has been chosen.	Medium - High	Medium
Cluster sampling	Sample all secondary units of a two-stage sampling scheme.	Estimation of total abundance. Maximising chance of detection.	Method for choosing primary units.	Particularly beneficial for clustered populations and will be inefficient otherwise.	Medium	Low (if units to be sampled are clustered).
Adaptive cluster sampling	If sample a positive outcome, continue sampling all neighbouring units.		Method for choosing primary units.	Particularly beneficial for rare clustered populations and will be inefficient for frequent or non-clustered	Medium	Low (if units to be sampled are clustered).

¹ Potential Practical Cost is the assumed cost if the population of interest satisfies the underlying assumptions for each sampling design. In particular, the level of cost will be correlated to the number of samples required in order to obtain the necessary output. For example, fewer samples will be needed in a stratified sampling scheme compared to a simple random scheme. Equally, estimated maps based on samples from accurate model predictions will require fewer samples to obtain the same accuracy as maps based on a systematic sampling scheme, although the cost of designing a model based sampling scheme will be higher.

				events.			
Disproportionate sampling	Sample at a higher frequency in strata with a higher density.		Strata information, knowledge of density within strata.	Particularly beneficial for sampling rare events.	Medium	Low (if strata knowledge is correct).	
Sequential sampling	Continue sampling procedure until some criteria are satisfied.	Estimation of the scarcity of a certain population characteristic.	Well defined stopping criteria or threshold value.	Particularly beneficial for sampling rare events.	Low	Unknown – depends on the stopping threshold as to how many samples will be required.	
Composite sampling	Pool a number of samples together and only separate if the composite tests positive for some criteria.	Detection of CaLsol infection within sampled specimens.	Criteria for a positive test.	Particularly beneficial for sampling rare events, especially if expensive to obtain samples.	Low	Low	
Methods for Prediction and Spatial Mapping of Population Characteristics							
Systematic sampling	Take sample at regularly spaced intervals.	Map of (any) spatially varying characteristic, e.g.: - CaLsol outbreaks - Psyllid density Within fields or across larger regions.		No underlying periodicity.	Low	High, likely to need large number of sampling points.	
Stratified systematic	Take samples at regularly spaced intervals (at different frequencies) within strata.		Strata information.	No periodicity within each stratum.	Low - Medium	Medium (if strata knowledge is correct).	
Adaptive cluster sampling	If sample a positive outcome, continue sampling all neighbouring units.		Method for choosing primary units.	Require a good sampling scheme for the primary units to limit the number of missed clusters.	Medium	Low (if units to be sampled are clustered).	
Model-based stratification	Stratified sampling where strata are determined via a model.		Auxiliary variates. Model for the stratification.	All model based methods will be limited by the accuracy of the corresponding model. In particular, initial data samples will be required in order to first construct an appropriate model in order to inform monitoring procedures.	Medium - High	Low, with potentially high benefits.	
Variogram modelling	Construct model of spatial dependence.		Variogram model.		Medium	Low	
Population modelling	Construct model of population dynamics.		Map of psyllid density.		Population model and auxiliary information such as host distribution.	High	Low
Invasive species distribution modelling	Construct model of population dynamics and spread.		Map of psyllid density (and invasion).		Population and spread model and auxiliary	High	Low

			information such as host distribution.			
Risk-based sampling	Construct model of risk.	Map of predicted risk of CaLsol infection.	Covariate information such as a measure of epidemic risk and epidemic dispersal. Spatial model for risk.		Medium - High	Low
Epidemic modelling	Construct model of epidemic dynamics.	Map of predicted presences of CaLsol infection.	Epidemic model. Host map and other data.		Medium - High	Low
Distance based and map based model	Sample n hosts closest to the last detection.	Map of predicted spread of CaLsol.	Host map.		Low	Low

1 INTRODUCTION TO SAMPLING

There are many aspects one needs to consider in order to design an efficient sampling procedure (Webster and Lark, 2012; Cochran 1953), which we summarise below with specific attention given to the main objectives of the monitoring strategies identified in the previous section.

1. **Variable of interest** (which might be psyllids, fields, host plants, infection)

Before sampling takes place, the first requirement is to define the variable to be measured through sampling. There are a number of different examples one could consider, depending on both the objective and scale of any monitoring scheme. For example;

- To monitor for the detection of psyllid migration to Scotland, the variable of interest would be the psyllid.
- To monitor the infestation of psyllids, the variable of interest would again be the psyllids
- To monitor an epidemic of CaLsol, one might sample for either CaLsol positive competent vectors or CaLsol positive potatoes.

2. **Domain (frame)**

The domain is defined as the population one wishes to sample. For instance, if one is interested in sampling potatoes, the domain may consist of all potato fields in Scotland, or possibly only those fields above a certain size. If, however, one was interested in sampling the psyllid vector, the domain may consist of the entirety of Scotland or perhaps only the arable farmland within Scotland.

3. **Units**

The units of sampling partition the domain of interest. For example, the units could be hectares or 5mx5m quadrats. Equally, if the domain of interest consisted of the arable farmland; the sampling units may be the individual fields (or even individual plants).

4. **Aim of sampling**

In broad terms, there are three main aims one might have for constructing a sampling procedure:

- a) Estimation of some characteristic of the population, e.g. total abundance of psyllids, average abundance of psyllids, the proportion of the population with a certain feature, such as proportion of carrot fields with psyllids detected.
- b) Detection of some characteristic across the sampling region.
- c) Prediction of some characteristic of the population across the entire sampling region, such as the predicted psyllid abundance, the predicted proportion of infected psyllids or the predicted risk of an epidemic occurrence.

Although all three aims may be of interest, the sampling procedure cannot be optimal for all three simultaneously. For instance, in order to estimate certain characteristics of the population, it is often essential to incorporate a random component into the sampling procedure (Section 2). In contrast, a sampling design that maximises the probability of detection of a species or predicting the density of a species at unknown locations can often be achieved through a model-based framework (Section 3).

5. **Tolerance of estimates**

The tolerance is defined to be the maximum level of uncertainty that can be associated with the sampling. This is intrinsically linked to the sample size requirements, as larger samples will give a lower level of uncertainty. In addition, the structure of the sampling design can improve the level of uncertainty for fixed sample sizes (Section 2).

6. **Cost**

The above specifications can always be defined with respect to the scientific question of interest. Undoubtedly however, the cost and practical implementation will also have an effect on the design of any sampling procedure. For example, there may be logistical constraints or accessibility issues, such as inaccessible fields to sample within. In addition, the overall number of samples might be

constrained and in terms of practical implementation the method of measurement, be it water trap, sticky trap or suction trap will be highly influential in any specific design for psyllid monitoring.

The above considerations will greatly impact the design of an efficient sampling procedure. This review aims to give an insight into the different sampling methodologies available. Section 2 reviews sampling methods for the estimation of a specific population characteristic whilst Section 3 focusses on methods designed for prediction and detection. In both cases, particular attention is given to the issues arising when sampling for rare or invasive events. In Section 4, we consider some practical issues surrounding the implementation of a sampling procedure and the considerations to take account of before designing a specific sampling procedure.

2 SAMPLING FOR ESTIMATION

The most common characteristics to estimate from a sample are:

- The total population size
- The average population size per unit area or density of the population
- The proportion of the population with some predefined characteristic. For example, the proportion of potato fields containing psyllids or the proportion of psyllids testing positive for CaLsol

Since sampling is used when the entire domain cannot be observed, the above quantities have to be estimated from a sample of the population. The most important feature of this sample is its representativeness. In particular, representativeness can be described by two properties,

- The **bias**. If a sample is representative, any calculation based on this sample should be unbiased (or accurate) for the entire population. For example consider calculating the average psyllid density per area. If units were only sampled in high psyllid density areas, the estimate would be biased concluding psyllid density to be high everywhere.
- The **variance**. If a sample is representative, the variance of the sample should be the same or at least similar to the variance of the entire population. For example if samples were taken only from “average” units, the estimated density would be more uniform than reality, since the variability in the sampled units is underestimated.

Thus, to obtain a representative sample, units should be selected at random according to some probability (*probabilistic sampling*). If the probability of inclusion is equal for all units within the population, the sampling procedure is termed *simple random sampling*. A brief intuition into why probabilistic sampling is advantageous to non-random sampling for estimating population characteristics is demonstrated in Figure 2. This figure shows two sampling schemes for soil samples within a ploughed field where in a) the samples have been chosen from a simple random sampling scheme to give a representative sample of the field. In b) however, the sample has been chosen systematically (*systematic sampling*) along a grid and gives an unrepresentative sample due to the systematic placement of samples within the plough lines. This demonstrates a common drawback to systematic sampling; if the domain of interest has some periodicity that has not been properly accounted for, the subsequent estimates will be highly biased. Despite this, systematic sampling can be advantageous so long as the periodicity has been properly accounted for. In particular, it can be seen from Figure 2 that although the same number of points have been sampled in each example, the systematic sample gives a much more even coverage of the domain (no large areas are unsampled), which is particularly beneficial when the main aim is to detect or predict (see Section 3).

FIGURE 2: SIMPLE RANDOM SAMPLING VS SYSTEMATIC SAMPLING.

Two sampling designs for a ploughed field, where plough lines are indicated by the grey shaded region. In a) sampling points have been placed according to a simple random sampling design compared to b) where a systematic sampling scheme has placed a disproportionately large number of sampling points within the plough lines to give an unrepresentative sample.

FIGURE 3: SIMPLE RANDOM SAMPLING VS STRATIFIED RANDOM SAMPLING.

Two sampling schemes, designed to estimate the density of some underlying species, which preferentially lives within the indicated circle. In a) sampling points have been placed according to a simple random sampling design to give an unbiased estimate of population density. In b) a stratified sample has been taken, with an equal number of points sampled randomly within the circle and outside the circle to give an unbiased, more precise estimate of population density.

Although simple random sampling gives an unbiased estimate, one key requirement of sampling for estimation is to ensure the quantity of interest is estimated precisely. For example, estimating the total population is only informative if this estimate is known to a certain degree of precision. It is intuitive (and true) that for any given sampling design, larger sample sizes will yield more precise estimates, what is less clear is how large is large enough. Sampling designs are often compared based on the required sample size for a predefined level of precision. Fundamentally, these differences arise from certain characteristics of the underlying population. Consider, for example, Figure 3 where the underlying density of a species is higher within the central circle of a square field. In the first example, a simple random sample is taken and the overall density of the species is estimated. In the second example, a stratified random sample has been taken, where an equal number of samples have been taken randomly within the central circle and outside the circle. The density estimate based

on the second sample will be unbiased (as will the first), but will have greater precision, since the sampling procedure has taken into account some of the variability within the underlying population. In particular, there is greater variability between strata than within strata, defined by the circular boundary. Thus variations on random sampling can be tailored to different situations in order to obtain better sampling designs.

2.1 SAMPLING METHODS

In this section, we describe five different sampling frameworks and how these methods can be adapted for specific circumstances. For a complete list of different sampling methods, see Table 4 in the Appendix.

Stratified sampling - Stratified sampling is constructed by dividing the domain region into a set of smaller regions (called strata) with samples then taken at random from each subpopulation to give a representative, efficient sample of the population. Stratified sampling becomes more efficient when the variation within strata is less than the variation between strata as demonstrated in Figure 3.

More generally then, stratification can occur through *any* partition of the population of interest into smaller subpopulations. For example, fields may be stratified according to their crop. If each subpopulation is then sampled according to a simple random sampling procedure, the method is termed *stratified random sampling*. However, any number of different sampling methods can be incorporated within a stratified framework. In terms of estimation, stratification can yield more precise estimates if the sample size taken from each stratum is chosen depending on the variability of the underlying variable of interest. For example, if the psyllid population fluctuates more variedly in carrot fields than in potato fields, one would sample more often in carrot fields than potatoes. Stratification ensures each subpopulation is sampled with appropriate precision, which may not be given in a simple random sampling scheme. The fundamental problem is choosing the method of stratification. In some situations, this may be clear cut, such as on environmental variables or to minimise some logistical constraints. One method for choosing a stratification could be based on an auxiliary variable that is thought to be correlated with the variable of interest. For example, altitude may be correlated with total population count so that the domain can be split into three strata corresponding to low, medium and high altitude with random samples taken from each strata. In addition, stratified sampling can be extended to stratify according to more than one criterion to result in a *multiple stratification sampling* procedure. Some care needs to be taken to ensure that the number of individual strata does not exceed the number of units within the population which is addressed in Cochran (1953). In terms of estimation, the calculations become simpler when one chooses two units per strata through a paired selection design (Moser and Kalton, 1971).

Multi-phase sampling – Multi-phase sampling can take many forms, but at its most fundamental level uses auxiliary information to inform either the estimation procedure or sampling design about the quantity of interest. For example, Yates (1981) describes an example of multi-phase sampling where at the first phase, one collects data on a large proportion of the population which can then be used to stratify the population of interest at phase two. For example, one could collect acreage information on farms at phase one and stratify according to farm size at phase two, to allow a stratified sampling scheme of potato fields. In comparison, Cochran (1953) describes multi-phase sampling where one again collects auxiliary information on a large proportion of the population and then subsamples these units to collect information on the variable of interest. From this, one can then map the auxiliary information to the population of interest to estimate this population through its relationship to the auxiliary data. Thus, multi-phase sampling consists of collecting levels of information on increasingly smaller subsamples of the population as depicted in Figure 4. For example, consider sampling fields for the presence of psyllids, where at phase 1, all fields are sampled and their altitude is measured, at phase 2, a subsample is taken and their precipitation levels are measured and finally at phase 3 a subsample of the fields sampled in phase 2 is taken and one measures the psyllid presence.

FIGURE 4: DEPICTION OF MULTI-PHASE SAMPLING

At phase 1, all fields are sampled and their altitude is measured. At phase 2, a subsample of these fields is selected and precipitation levels are measured. Finally at phase 3, a further subsample is taken and the main variable of interest (e.g. psyllid presence) is measured.

FIGURE 5: DEPICTION OF MULTI-STAGE SAMPLING

At stage 1, a sample of “large” primary units is selected. At stage 2, within those chosen primary units, a sample of secondary units is selected. Finally at stage 3, within the selected secondary units, the main units of interest (e.g. fields) are sampled.

In this way, one can then estimate psyllid presence at the fields sampled only in phases 1 and 2 by investigating the relationship between precipitation, altitude and psyllid presence in the fields sampled at phase 3.

Multi-stage sampling – Multi-stage sampling (also referred to as nested sampling designs or hierarchical sampling (Webster and Lark, 2012)) occurs when the population is partitioned into a hierarchy of sampling units. For instance, the population is first divided into a small number of primary units which in turn can be partitioned into a set of secondary sampling units. Multi-stage sampling then proceeds by first sampling a selection of primary units and then for each of the selected primary units, a sample of their corresponding secondary units is collected. For example, one first selects a sample of farms within Scotland and then for each farm samples a certain number of fields. One key consideration in the multi-stage sampling procedures is the selection of the secondary units. In particular, it may be that there is a great deal of variability in the secondary units and it may be beneficial from an estimation viewpoint to sample more secondary units from the farm with greater variability than the farm with uniform fields. Nested sampling provides an efficient method to estimate the contributions made to the variation at disparate spatial scales. In particular, Webster and Lark (2012) discuss balanced and unbalanced designs and also methods for optimising the allocation of unbalanced nested sampling models.

Cluster sampling – Cluster sampling is a special case of multi-stage sampling where for each primary unit sampled, all the corresponding secondary sampling units are sampled. For example, after selecting a sample of farms, all their fields are included in the sampling procedure. This sampling method is often chosen as a method to reduce logistical costs, although it can come at a cost of decreased precision in the population estimates (Cochran, 1953).

Adaptive sampling – Adaptive sampling is another very general sampling method which at its fundamental level is any approach where the decision to continue sampling depends on what has already been sampled, i.e. data collection continues until some stopping rule is applied. Adaptive sampling has a natural framework for monitoring populations through time, but it will be shown in the following section that a number of adaptive methods, specifically *adaptive cluster sampling*, have been developed specifically to address the common issues related to sampling rare or elusive events. The main drawback to the adaptive techniques is that often, the final sample size is not known as it is not known in advance when the criteria for discontinuing sampling will be revealed. As a direct consequence to the unknown sample size, the final precision of the estimates cannot be controlled. These methods have therefore found much use in decision analysis rather than in estimation. For example, if more than 10 psyllids are detected than an intervention such as applying pesticides may be implemented.

A class of adaptive methods are the *sequential sampling designs*, where a probability based sampling scheme is used to select units until some condition is satisfied, for example, until at least 10 competent psyllid vectors have been detected. The advantage of the sequential design is that it is known in advance how many psyllids will be found but not how many units will need to be sampled.

2.2 ASPECTS RELATED TO RARE EVENTS

The sampling frameworks introduced above provide the basic building blocks for any sampling scheme with the estimation of some population characteristic in mind. However, there are serious shortcomings to these methods when the species of interest is rare or elusive, such as psyllids. For these species, the above methods will be highly inefficient as most sampling units will be empty (which could be sticky or water traps from individual fields). There have been a number of techniques developed to overcome these limitations which are described below.

Disproportionate sampling – Disproportionate sampling, as described in Kalton and Anderson (1986), is a stratification method whereby if certain strata are thought to have a higher density of the rare species, it may be more efficient to sample at a higher frequency in these more highly concentrated strata in order to estimate abundance or prevalence.

Composite sampling – Composite sampling is an approach more beneficial to high cost measurement procedures in combination with sampling for a rare species. For example, it may be of interest to test for CaLsol in plant material but the test is expensive. In this scenario, the plant samples from different sampling units could be bulked together and the laboratory test would be performed once. Only if this test is positive would the individual samples be tested. Consequently, this will be a more economical procedure for rare events (Barnett, 2004), although the quality of information will be reduced.

Adaptive cluster sampling – Adaptive cluster sampling (Thompson and Seber, 1996) is an advantageous procedure for sampling rare clustered populations. This scheme first takes a sample of units from the population (from any of the sampling methods described in Section 2.1, e.g. simple random, stratified or systematic sampling) and if the species is present in the unit, all neighbouring units are sampled. This continues until each species positive unit is surrounded by empty units. This approach is particularly good at estimating total abundance, and in addition logistically advantageous since samples are taken in clusters. However, a major drawback is that the final sample size is random and will depend upon the spatial

distribution of the underlying population. For instance, it will be more efficient for populations that are geographically rare and clustered. If a species is not rare, then the number of units sampled will be large since there will be relatively few empty units, in which case a simple random sampling or stratified sampling scheme with fewer units may yield a similarly precise estimate. There have been a number of extensions to adaptive cluster sampling to overcome the issue of uncertainty in the final sample size such as implementing a stopping rule when the total number of observations exceeds some threshold, although this will introduce bias into the corresponding population estimators.

Neighbourhood free sampling – A disadvantage to the adaptive cluster design is that there is some redundancy since sampling only stops once every cluster has been surrounded by sampled (but empty) units. One way to reduce this redundancy is to use a neighbourhood free sampling design such as *adaptive allocation* or *two-stage sequential sampling*. Adaptive allocation is a two stage sampling scheme where the primary units are sampled by stratified random sampling and secondary units are sampled with a higher frequency in the strata with higher variance. In comparison, two stage sequential sampling is where the secondary units are only sampled from the primary units with a certain characteristic. For example, consider farms to be the primary units and secondary units are the corresponding fields. However, only the secondary units from a farm with at least one psyllid detection are considered for selection. Adaptive two-stage sequential designs have also been developed specifically for sampling rare clustered populations such as blue-winged teal (Brown et al. 2008). These designs are an amalgamation of both two-stage sequential designs and adaptive allocation. In particular, the numbers of secondary units in the two-stage design are chosen based on the measured level of the primary unit. For example, if farms are again considered to be the primary units, the number of secondary units (e.g. plant samples) chosen to sample from each farm is based on the number of spruce trees (the overwintering habitat of psyllids) within a 5 mile radius.

All of the above designs can be combined in a multitude of ways. For example, the population could be stratified into two types of unit, units where it is likely to find the event of interest, in which case a simple random sampling scheme may be used, and units where the event is likely to be rare in which case an adaptive cluster sampling scheme could be implemented. In addition, one may combine sampling schemes over different variables, for instance the adaptation criteria of whether to continue sampling or not, may be based on some auxiliary variable (a rapid assessment variable), such as habitat and then only in those final chosen sampling units is the variable of interest sampled (Thompson, 2004).

So far, only extensions to the sampling *design* have been considered to better account for rare or elusive events. There are of course a number of other extensions outlined below.

Frame Modelling - One way to account for rare events is to refine the definition of the domain. For instance, if estimates of the domain boundaries, such as the altitude at which a rare species may occur, can be obtained then the domain may be restricted to these areas and standard sampling procedures, such as simple random sampling, can be effectively employed. This technique has been termed *frame modelling* (Kalton and Anderson 1986) since the domain has been reduced to sampling from a smaller frame.

Estimation Variable - An alternative to redefining the domain is to redefine the variable of interest. For example, threshold sampling provides an alternative, whereby the interest lies in estimating the proportion of units exceeding some threshold rather than total abundance. This is similar to binomial sampling, where the number of successes (number exceeding a certain threshold) in the total number of sampling units is estimated. This is a less costly method (Binns et al., 2000) since it is only required to count up until some threshold. One example of this is *presence/absence sampling* where the threshold is just a single detection. There is clearly some loss of information as it becomes harder to estimate total abundance, but as stated in Binns et al. (2000), the amount of information lost can be assessed against the cost gained. A similar example is given by *patch-occupancy sampling*, where the objective is to estimate the occupancy of each sampling unit (Thompson, 2004).

Detection Probability - A major consideration with any method aiming to estimate characteristics of a rare (or indeed any) species is the detection probability. This is the probability that given the species is present, it can be detected. A common aspect often found with rare species, is their elusiveness. Within the literature this is thought of in terms of incomplete detectability, that even if a unit is sampled, not all objects will be observed. As pointed out by Thompson (2004), estimation of abundance critically depends on the estimation of the detection probability under the sampling method, thus there has been much research into models of the detection probability. In particular, detection probabilities are often expressed as functions of covariate information such as habitat. Patch-occupancy models (Thompson, 2004) provide an approach for evaluating the detection probability based on repeated visits to a site to gain information on the detection/non-detection.

2.3 TEMPORALLY RESOLVED DATA

The above sampling procedures have focussed on obtaining representative samples at a single point in time. It is natural to consider the extension to sampling over time. The main objective then is typically either to;

- Estimate any *change* in a population characteristic such as total abundance or density.
- Estimate the *average* over time of a population characteristic.

Cochran (1953) showed that for estimating change it is better to sample the **same** units in each round (or bout) of sampling. In contrast, for estimating the average over time, it is better to sample a **new** set of units in each sampling round.

One reason for wishing to estimate change over time is to gain an estimate of the population dynamics over different seasons or to use population density estimates to forecast future populations and consequently to provide information for pest management. For example, Binns et al. (2000) use time sequential sampling to estimate the parameters of population growth curves. These parameters were then used to classify the growth curve into either an endemic, in which case no action was taken, or outbreak curve, where containment measures should be put in place.

In the above we assume that sampling will take place at known time points. The principles guiding the decision of these time points will be the same as those regarding sampling the spatial units. For instance time points may be chosen at random in the season or at equidistant points. When sampling units over time, the temporal time points are usually chosen systematically, as this will give even coverage, although care should be taken to ensure the time interval does not correlate to any periodicity in the population dynamics.

Binns et al. (2000) discuss a time-adaptive sampling scheme. The main objective in this work was to monitor pest populations over time and to assess when containment measures should be employed. If the population is low for long periods of time, it is inefficient to sample at short intervals. Thus one approach is *alternative time sampling*. In this method, at each time point, the pest population was sampled and categorised into one of three categories; a) low, b) intermediate or c) high risk. If the population was high risk, containment measures were put in place. If however, the risk was intermediate, the population was sampled at the next time point. If the risk was low, it was deemed that a longer time interval should pass and the population was not sampled again until the third round of sampling, and so on. This method can easily be extended to incorporate more levels of risk. Thus, the method is more cost-effective as samples are only taken when the population is close to the threshold of action.

2.4 AUXILIARY DATA

Auxiliary data can provide important information for designing efficient sampling procedures. For example, Guisan and Zimmermann (2000) and references therein describe how preliminary studies can be used to discover appropriate variables that can be used for effective stratification. As an example, auxiliary data may be obtained regarding the individual geographical layers, such as altitude and rainfall, which can then be used to stratify the area into a number of subareas from which random samples can be taken.

In addition to aiding the design of the sampling procedures, auxiliary data can be used to improve the estimation of population characteristics through both ratio estimators and regression estimators. The details of these procedures are covered in many standard texts including Cochran (1953) with the main idea based on correlating an auxiliary variable, which is measured on a large sample of the population, to the variable of interest, measured on a smaller sample, which then enables the variable of interest to be inferred on a wider population. Consequently, auxiliary data can be used to predict the presence or abundance of a species at unknown locations, so long as those locations have measurements of the auxiliary data.

Auxiliary information (Thompson, 2004) can also be used to construct *directed sampling designs*. These designs choose sampling units along the gradients of the covariate information, e.g. environmental gradients, in order to maximise the coverage over a certain covariate. For example, a sampling scheme may be designed to sample locations over a range of possible altitudes.

3 SAMPLING FOR PREDICTION

The previous section described sampling procedures that can be used to obtain estimates of certain characteristics of an underlying population. However, estimating population characteristics may be of secondary importance for initial monitoring strategies. In particular, it may be of greater importance to predict the spatial location of psyllid presence in order to maximise the detection probability of competent vectors. As with the standard classical sampling literature, there is a huge literature regarding sampling methods for prediction.

Assuming the existence of spatial correlation in the population density (i.e. points that lie close to each other are likely to have similar characteristics), spatial predictions at unknown locations will be more precise the closer they are to known locations. Consequently, a regular grid (i.e. a systematic sample) will provide even spatial coverage (compared to a probabilistic sample) and will consequently provide a better predictive map than the random sampling methods discussed in the previous section. However, a regular grid does not take into account any knowledge of the specific form of the spatial dependency. For instance, if the population is clustered, a better sampling scheme will be to sample the boundaries of these clusters. Thus, if there is prior knowledge regarding the spatial dependency in the underlying populations, predictions will be improved through *model-based sampling*, where the sampling scheme is designed to account for the underlying spatial dependencies.

This is a fundamentally different problem to the sampling approach for estimation described in the previous section as the characteristic has to be additionally predicted at unsampled locations. There are at least two steps in any model-based approach to sampling. The first is to construct the model and the second is to use the model to predict. If an intervention is required based on these predictions, a third step is taken. For example, when designing a sampling procedure for detection, the model predictions will inform the locations to sample in order to maximise the probability of detecting psyllids. At each of these steps a different sampling problem can be considered;

FIGURE 6: ITERATIVE SAMPLING SCHEME FOR MODEL CONSTRUCTION AND PREDICTION

Four sampling aims can be identified in the model-based approach; 1) Sample to construct the model, 2) Sample to improve the model, 3) Sample to improve model predictions and 4) Sampling associated with model predictions, for example to identify locations within the domain to apply an intervention policy.

- Where should one sample in order to gain most information of the model structure (albeit this may come from literature and expert knowledge),
- Given a model, where should a sample be taken in order to obtain the most precise predictions,
- Given the predictions, where should an intervention be implemented. For example, an intervention may be to find locations to optimise the detection of psyllids or to find the locations where containment measures should be put in place to reduce the impact of an epidemic.

Figure 6 shows the processes involved in constructing a model in order to design a specific sampling scheme for a particular intervention based on model predictions. In particular, a model is constructed based on initial data, possibly from an initial sampling scheme. From this model, additional information can be collected to improve the model, for example, sampling in previously unsampled strata. Predictions can then be calculated based on the constructed model. This may then identify additional locations to sample, for example, locations with a large uncertainty in the predicted outcome. Finally, a sampling scheme can be designed based on the predicted outcomes. For instance, to design a sampling scheme to maximise the number of psyllids captured, the model would predict the locations of highest density so that sampling in these locations would maximise the probability of detection.

In the following sections, we focus on the issues surrounding model construction and the different choices available and how the appropriateness of each model may depend on the main study objective.

3.1 SPATIAL MAPPING

Spatial mapping refers to the process of constructing a continuous map of some characteristic of a population, for example, a map of the psyllid density, or a map of the risk of a high-impact epidemic over the entire domain of interest. There are two approaches to model-based spatial mapping; geostatistical models and dynamic models.

3.1.1 GEOSTATISTICAL MODELS

Geostatistical models view the underlying spatial distribution as a stochastic process, which is described through the correlation between spatial locations. Modelling the dependence or correlation between points is done using a variogram. The variogram describes how similar the density will be in locations at various distances apart. The variogram can be estimated from data and then a model fitted. Webster and Lark (2012) provide the following guidelines for sampling with the aim of variogram estimation;

- The maximum distance between sampling points should be chosen to account for most of the spatial variation according to prior knowledge.
- The pairwise distances between sampling points (the lag) should be sufficiently distributed between the minimum and maximum distance of interest, i.e. aim to have at least 10 or more lag distances. If in addition, the main interest is to predict once the variogram has been estimated, more sampling points should be placed close together. For example, at each sampling point add an additional point close by.
- To ensure there is sufficient data to estimate the variogram, there should be at least 150-200 sampling points.

There are many different variogram models within the literature that can describe different shapes to the spatial dependence.

The spatial dependence described by the variogram, can be used to predict the variable of interest at unsampled locations. This process of spatial prediction is known as *kriging*. There are different types of kriging varying from block kriging (prediction on a grid), indicator kriging (prediction of a presence/absence response), disjunctive kriging (prediction of the probability of a presence or absence response) to universal kriging (general prediction of spatial trend) (Barnett, 2004). The advantage of kriging over other methods of spatial prediction is that estimates are unbiased and have minimum prediction variance, which leads to minimum uncertainty. Thus, additional points may be sampled if there is a lot of uncertainty about the prediction in certain locations (Webster and Lark, 2012). In general, it is desirable to have a sampling scheme that minimises the error in the predictions. This can be found through numerical search algorithms (Marchant and Lark, 2006).

Consequently, in order to construct a map of the predicted density, there has to be a division of sampling effort between optimising variogram estimation and optimising precise predictions. One solution would be to have a multi-phase sampling design where sampling points are continually updated as depicted in Figure 6. An alternative would be to define a sampling procedure of a mixture of points, half are chosen systematically (which is good although not optimal) for prediction and half are chosen to optimise the estimation of the variogram model.

3.1.2 DYNAMIC MODELS

Dynamic models in contrast to geostatistical models, explicitly take into account the mechanisms driving the spatial distribution of the variable of interest. Whilst reviewing the literature, we identified three classes of dynamic models that had relevance to this project. These approaches can be categorised according to the main variable used for mapping. These were *population dynamic models*, where the main mapping quantity is the population density, *epidemic models*, which map the incidence of disease and *risk models*, which map the risk of a certain event.

3.1.2.1 POPULATION DYNAMIC MODELS

Population models have been used for many years with perhaps the most famous example being the Lotka-Volterra model which models the temporal changes in population levels of a simple predator-prey system. Models have been developed for many systems and can incorporate complex system dependences including, host-parasite or host-vector-parasite interactions. In order to construct a dynamic model, substantial information regarding the system of interest is required. For the system in mind, a dynamic model of psyllid population should include the following components;

- Migratory dynamics (overwinter dispersal).
- Dispersal dynamics during summer.
- Temporal population dynamics such as population growth rate (including birth, death and predation dynamics).

- Spatial distribution of hosts and the interacting dynamics between host and vector.

The particularly complex component for this project is the variety in dynamics for the individual psyllid species. For instance, *B. trigonica* has two to three generations per year whilst *T. apicalis* has only one generation per year (Haapalainen, 2014). Thus the usefulness of population dynamic models for initial monitoring will be limited but may become more relevant if an outbreak occurs and a particular psyllid species can be identified as the transmitting vector.

As with the geostatistical models, once a dynamic model has been developed, predictions of the population levels in the surrounding areas can be obtained to create a map of likely population density. These predictions can then be used to highlight areas likely to have the highest abundance which may be desirable locations to focus the sampling effort for monitoring or intervention purposes.

3.1.2.2 EPIDEMIC MODELS

There have been numerous papers modelling the spatial distribution of various epidemics. For example, Parry et al. (2014) developed a model of huanglongbing (HLB) disease incorporating dispersal via psyllid vectors. Mechanistic models of this kind allow the investigation of different parameterisations, for example, the authors investigated the effects of different latency periods and different dispersal characteristics on the epidemic progression through simulations. As with population dynamic models, epidemic models need to incorporate various sources of information to properly account for the complexity of the system. Appendix E and Sjölund et al. (2015) summarise the available literature regarding the interaction between the pathogen, the host and the vector.

Dynamic models require a much greater knowledge of the mechanisms driving the species of interest compared to geostatistical or classical sampling. Consequently, a major question is how much (if anything) is gained by implementing such a sampling scheme. Demon et al. (2011) investigated how the development of a spatially explicit stochastic epidemic model for *P. ramorum* (the causal agent of sudden oak death) compared to a) distance-based sampling (sample n hosts closest to the eradication zone), b) simple random sampling and c) stratified random sampling. In this example, knowledge of the epidemic parameters was obtained from experts and allowed the authors to focus on the dispersal characteristics. The method implemented in this paper guarantees an optimal sampling design that maximises the probability to detect conditional on having i) the correct epidemic model, ii) simulations to test the proposed dispersal characteristics and iii) a numerical optimisation method. They showed that distance-based and predicted epidemic map sampling both give a probability of detection close to the maximum and were much better than either random or stratified sampling schemes.

In contrast to the above, Parnell et al. (2011) developed a model-based procedure for predicting the epidemic response without the need to explicitly develop a full epidemic model. In this work, the authors restricted the modelling to the dispersal process of the pathogen and the spatial availability of the host. Thus, the probability of disease was based on the distance to hosts with and without the disease. This differs from the epidemic modelling approach above, as no temporal component is explicitly included. It was shown in both Parnell et al. (2011) and Luo et al. (2012) that these methods outperformed geostatistical models with indicator kriging although it should be noted that this was based on a random sample rather than a targeted sampling design. This improvement over geostatistical models implies that accounting for the mechanism of dispersal is advantageous.

Any model-based approach has the disadvantage of susceptibility to model misspecification. For instance in the paper by Parnell et al. (2011) the model-based approaches are unable to predict the isolated epidemic outbreaks and consequently would never sample these locations. However, if an additional random sampling scheme was incorporated in conjunction with the model-based sampling design, these isolated outbreaks have a greater chance of discovery.

3.1.2.3 RISK MODELS

An interesting development in the literature is that of *risk-based sampling/mapping*. Rather than modelling the epidemic itself, this approach focusses on identifying high-risk locations in a landscape (Parnell et al., 2014). This method was developed to identify a sampling procedure to detect outbreaks of a disease where sampling effort could be focussed on those areas deemed to have the highest impact if the disease was detected. For example, Parnell et al. (2014) defined risk to be the probability that the pathogen would arrive and cause an epidemic multiplied by the size of the epidemic if it occurred in that location. This was developed for HLB disease so that high-risk locations would be sampled and if the disease was detected the sampled areas would be treated. Despite the specificity of the application, the method was developed generically to model the risk of **any** epidemic, provided there is a) a measure of epidemic size, b) the dispersal mechanism of the disease and c) a map of the host landscape.

Risk-based models differ from the population dynamic models with an additional level of uncertainty through “the hypothetical”. Explicitly, risk-based models ask the question, *if* the event were present at this location, what would be the result. This overlays the dynamical model of *how* the event gets to each location. Consequently, these models are beneficial for developing sampling schemes for detection as one explicitly incorporates the likelihood of an invasion occurring. In the simplest framework, this likelihood will depend on habitat suitability (the more suitable, the more likely psyllids will thrive) but external risks such as import hotspots, trade networks and sources of migration may also be incorporated.

3.2 SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS

The previous section discussed models that took explicit account of the spatial dependence in the underlying species distribution. Whether that was through a non-mechanistic variogram model or mechanistic dynamic model, it enables predictions to be obtained on some quantity of interest over the whole spatial domain. In contrast, this section reviews methods developed for predictive modelling without explicitly accounting for spatial dependence. These species distribution models are referred to in a number of different guises including predictive, regression and habitat suitability models.

In order to construct a predictive model auxiliary or covariate data are required since the spatial dependency is no longer explicitly incorporated. Species distribution models correlate presence/absence data to environmental variables such as rainfall or temperature. These models may be used to predict further likely locations, for instance, Austin (2007) describes how these relationships can be constructed using regression models such as generalized linear models or generalized additive models. Williams et al. (2009) noted that since rare species frequently have small distributions and small sample sizes, there are likely to be power issues that may compromise model robustness. Consequently, random forest, artificial neural net and maximum entropy (Stohlgren and Schnase, 2006) methods may perform better.

The aim of species distribution models is often to identify and estimate the environmental niche of a species (also termed habitat suitability models). Consequently, Guisan et al. (2006) describe an iterative procedure between sampling and modelling to improve estimation. In particular, the niche models inform the subsequent sampling procedure by producing a map of habitat suitability, which can then be stratified into areas according to the predicted probability of presence and absence. The subsequent sampling round takes an equal number of samples from each stratum in order to improve the model. If the aim was to detect species from this round of sampling rather than model improvement samples would only be taken in the strata with predicted presence.

Extensions and adjustments to this set of models are common in the literature. For example, the sampling can be adjusted so that the stratified sampling is constrained to be a minimum distance apart to ensure sampling of a different population (Crall et al., 2013).

Although these models have been used for rare species (Thompson, 2004), there is an inherent difficulty since the predictive accuracy will depend on the prevalence. Specifically, the rarer the species the more likely the model is to produce false positives (low model sensitivity) (Inglis et al., 2006). These models rely on initial data or an iterative modelling-sampling scheme in order to produce predictions. Inglis et al. (2006) describe a habitat suitability index model suited to species with no initial data where the aim is to target surveillance efforts. This is based on an index of habitat quality obtained from information within the literature and expert knowledge. Interestingly, this was extended to incorporate a dispersion model from the likely points of invasion in order to find where species would accumulate.

3.3 STRATIFICATION/CLASSIFICATION

Stratified sampling was previously discussed as a design to enable estimation of a population characteristic. In addition, *model-based stratification* can be used in sampling schemes for both detection and prediction. For example, if the landscape can be modelled such that different components can be classified as more or less amenable to the species, disproportionate sampling can be used to sample in those strata that are more likely to contain the species. Edwards et al. (2005) implemented this approach for rare species. First they obtained presence/absence data from a more abundant but related species and then related this auxiliary species to a set of predictors (here topographical variables) of the rare species. Using these relationships, they were able to derive strata to sample for the rare species and increase the detection probability of the sample.

3.4 AFTER MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Once a model has been developed, the subsequent sampling scheme will take one of the following forms:

- For model improvement, sampling should be focussed at new locations some of which are of similar type to those in the model and some of which are not.
- For prediction improvement, sampling should be focussed at those locations with highest predictive variance.
- For intervention, samples should be taken purposively at the locations the model has identified as most likely. For example, if the aim is to sample as many events as possible (i.e. detection), sampling should be focussed at locations with highest predicted probability of presence or highest abundance. In contrast, if the intervention is to apply a pesticide to minimise the risk of an epidemic spreading, the intervention should be applied at locations with risk predicted to be higher than some predetermined threshold.

One consideration to bear in mind when allocating sampling effort for the detection of new events is that it may be worth spreading resources more evenly so that there is only one detection per cluster (Parnell et al., 2014) rather than always sampling at locations of highest abundance. Consequently, when designing the sampling scheme additional constraints should be implemented to ensure a minimum separation between sampling points.

3.5 TEMPORALLY RESOLVED DATA

A temporal component can be introduced by repeated rounds of sampling. There are different implementations of temporal sampling depending on the aim. For population dynamic models, sampling may be focussed in order to improve the accuracy of the dynamic model such as refining the estimated growth rate. In this scenario, the same units should be sampled over time, but perhaps should be taken at the time points of the greatest change in the population dynamics. If, however, the aim is to map the spread of an invasion over time as in the epidemic models, new sampling units should be chosen according to their predicted likelihood of having the disease.

3.6 ASPECTS FOR ESTIMATION

Sampling methods designed for efficient prediction are, in general, highly inefficient at providing estimates of population characteristics compared to the sampling procedures outlined in Section 2. What is worse is that they often produce biased estimates. Having said this, there are several sampling methods which can be used for both prediction and estimation.

- Systematic sampling via a regular grid, although not optimal for either estimation or prediction, can produce reasonable results for both.
- Model-based stratification, where strata are defined from a model, but sampling within strata is either random or systematic. Note that for estimation, one should assign the number of samples taken from each strata based on the within strata variability but for detection, more samples should be taken from strata with a higher likelihood of presence.
- Weighted random sampling, a random sampling scheme is employed where sampling units are selected with probability proportional to weights based on model predictions. Estimation of population characteristics can be obtained from weighted random samples, although will not be optimal.

4 PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR SAMPLE DESIGN

Although sampling procedures should be designed to address the main scientific question of interest, there are also practical considerations as discussed below.

4.1 AUXILIARY DATA

In many of the methods we've described, in order to construct efficient sampling designs, substantial prior information is required. For example, to create a risk-based model, information would be required on the likely sources of invasion and the different trade networks. For the dynamic models, information is required on the dispersal characteristics such as psyllid jump distances. Thus, when considering a mechanistic modelling approach it is important to understand what information is required and the effort involved in obtaining it. Similar issues arise in the classical sampling procedures such as identifying the variables to be used for stratification (both within standard or model-based stratification) in a stratified random sampling scheme. To address this issue, we have compiled a list of the different auxiliary data types that might be required for some of the identified sampling procedures:

- The possible vectors and their spatial distribution, summarised in Sjölund et al. (2015).
- The associated hosts of each identified vector and their spatial distribution, information on which can be found in Sjölund et al. (2015) and Appendices B and C.
- The population dynamics of identified psyllid vectors, summarised in Appendix D.
- The dynamics and interactions of the pathogen CaLsol (see Appendix E).
- Likely sources of invasion (of infected host plants and/or psyllid vectors).
- Topographical and climate information which is freely available from a number of sources.

4.2 APPLICATION TO MONITORING AND INTERVENTION

A monitoring schedule can be constructed by repeated rounds of sampling. The structure of the repeated sampling has been shown to depend on the aim of the monitoring schedule and can take one of three forms;

- a) Independent samples (a new sample each time),
- b) Dependent samples (the new sample depends on the outcome of the first sample),

- c) Fixed sample (the same sample is taken each time).

Often associated with a monitoring schedule is an intervention programme. For instance, if the population density exceeds a certain threshold, an intervention takes place. Thus, mechanistic models can be useful in determining the intervention threshold so that initial sampling is designed to construct appropriate models (through fixed samples each time) and identify the key thresholds with subsequent sampling designed to monitor a representative sample (independent samples taken each time).

4.3 COST MODEL

Unrelated to the scientific question of interest, is the cost of sampling. In reality many factors will be traded off each other in designing a sampling scheme, not least of all is the cost. Factors impacting the cost (both in terms of effort as well as financial cost) are:

- The final sample size,
- The logistics of any sampling scheme, such as travelling between sampling sites. For instance, cluster sampling is much simpler logistically as groups of units are often co-located,
- The accessibility of samples. For example, it may be advantageous to constrain sampling to be within a certain distance to a road.

Thus any sampling scheme should try to minimise cost, whilst maximising efficiency or reliability of the results. Consequently, sampling schemes should be assessed through a simulation process prior to field sampling to assess the impact of any additional sampling constraints.

4.4 MEASUREMENT PROCESS

In much of the sampling literature, very little is dedicated to the issues surrounding the measurement process with the main exception being that of detectability. Detectability is defined by how likely a species is to be detected given it is already present. Thus, when collecting presence and absence data, it is unclear if an absence is simply a non-detection. One approach to estimating detectability is to return to the same sites multiple times and under various assumptions record the number of presences and absences (MacKenzie et al., 2002). Alternatively, information of similar species may be incorporated through a hierarchical approach (MacKenzie et al., 2005).

Imperfect detectability is intrinsically linked with the method of measurement and the spatial scale of individual units. For instance, if one was monitoring psyllid populations, sampling could be implemented in any of the following ways:

- If fields were to be considered as the smallest sampling unit, then abundance (or presence/absence) within that field will be estimated by either;
 - Collecting a sample of plants, from which psyllids could be identified, in which case detectability at the plant level will depend on how easily psyllids can be identified from plant material but at the field level, detectability within a field will depend on the number of plant samples take.
 - Counting psyllid frequencies from sticky traps within the field. Sticky traps will be subject to imperfect detectability, with different types of trap subject to different effectiveness. For instance Taylor et al. (2014) compared the effectiveness of different sticky traps for *B. cockerelli* and found that larger yellow traps with a green border yielded a higher density of catches than other types.
- If sampling was to be done using suction trap data, one could make use of known trapping efficiencies of aphids and how the suction trap data of aphids correlates to field samples (Fabre et al., 2010), in order to estimate similar information of psyllids.

In addition to imperfect detectability, there is the issue of measurement error. For instance, counts may be miscalculated or species may be misidentified. Consequently, when considering a sampling design, it is worth also incorporating a constraint linked to the measurement process. For instance, it may be much more accurate to count psyllids from water traps rather than sticky traps but the placement of the traps is less flexible.

5 SUMMARY

Within this review, we have characterised different sampling procedures by both the main purpose of the sampling (whether it's for estimation or prediction) and by the methodology (whether it's designed probabilistically or deterministically). Each of the methods reviewed is advantageous under different scenarios. For the estimation of a population characteristic the random sampling procedures reviewed within Section 2 should be used. If however, the main interest is in predicting a characteristic, regular or purposive methods will outperform the probabilistic designs. There are many variations within these different sampling frameworks and some care should be given to defining the main objectives of the study in order to develop the most appropriate sampling procedure.

It is likely that the most efficient sampling design for even a single objective will incorporate different facets of the sampling literature. For example, consider the objective of sampling potato crops for monitoring the spread of a CaLsol epidemic after an outbreak and intervention program. As stated in our recommendations, the sampling locations can be efficiently determined from a map of the predicted risk. However, this will only be appropriate for the sampling of primary units (such as fields) within a multi-stage design. The secondary units (potato plants within the high-risk fields) must also be sampled. This can be achieved, for example, in one of the following ways:

- a) Sample by a simple random sampling scheme.
- b) Sample by a stratified scheme.
- c) Sample on a regular pattern, for instance plants selected in a X across the field or a W or a regular grid.
- d) Samples taken purposively at the edge of the field, since psyllids have been found to preferentially locate at the field edges.

As stated in the introduction, the main aim of this review is to provide the necessary background to design the most appropriate sampling scheme for a particular objective as demonstrated in our recommendations. RRes has much experience in the design and implementation of a wide range of different sampling strategies and is well placed to provide further advice on the specific implementations.

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APPENDICES

A. SAMPLING APPROACHES

TABLE 4: SUMMARY OF THE DIFFERENT SAMPLING METHODS

	Sampling Method	Description	Aim	Auxiliary data required	Aspects of target species
Convenience	Encountered / opportunistic sampling	Record data “as and when” it is found. No sampling scheme is implemented	To obtain any information		
Non-random	Systematic sampling	Take sample at regularly spaced intervals	Estimation and mapping		No underlying periodicity
	Stratified systematic	Take samples at regularly spaced intervals (at different frequencies) within strata.	Estimation and mapping	Strata information	No periodicity within each strata
	Quota sampling	Take samples until reach a predetermined number of a set of characteristics.	Detection	Specific quota	
	Ranked set	Take a stratified sample where strata are determined as quartiles of the data. For example, lowest abundance, median and highest.	Estimation	Expert knowledge to determine strata classification	Expensive to sample since this reduces the total number of samples to take.
Probabilistic	Simple random sample	Each unit has equal probability of being sampled.	Estimation		
	Stratified random sampling	Take a random sample within each defined strata	Estimation	Strata information	Between strata variability higher than within strata variability.
	Multiple stratification	A composition of several stratifications.	Estimation	Strata information	
	Disproportionate sampling	Sample at a higher frequency in strata with a higher density.	Detection / Estimation of total abundance.	Strata information, knowledge of density within strata.	Rare

Paired selection design	Stratified sampling with two units per strata sampled	Estimation	Strata information	
Subsampling/two-stage sampling	Sample "large" primary units, within each primary unit, take a sample of secondary units (the units of interest)	Estimation	Hierarchy of unit "size". Domain can be partitioned into a hierarchy of units.	
Double sampling/two-phase sampling	Sample an auxiliary variable on a large number of units, then sample the variable of interest on a subset.	Estimation	An auxiliary, correlated variable.	
Cluster sampling	Sample all secondary units of a two-stage sampling scheme	Estimation		Clustered
Adaptive cluster sampling	If sample a positive outcome, continue sampling all neighbouring units.	Estimation		Rare clustered populations
Adaptive two-stage sequential	A two stage sampling scheme, where the number of secondary units sampled within each primary depends on the outcome of the primary samples.	Estimation		Rare clustered populations
Repeated sampling (fixed sample)	Repeatedly sample the same units multiple times.	Estimating change		
Repeated sampling (independent sample)	Repeatedly take a new sample over multiple times.	Estimating average over time		
Repeated sampling (sub sample)	Repeatedly subsample the same units multiple times.	Estimating means over time		
Repeated sampling (partial replacement)	Repeatedly sample a mixture of the same and new units over multiple times.	Estimating means over time		
Sequential sampling	Continue sampling procedure until some criteria is satisfied.	Decision Making	Stopping criteria - threshold value	Rare
Covariate directed sampling, e.g. gradsect	Sample along the gradient of identified covariates.	Prediction / detection. Information regarding habitat occupancy.	Covariates such as environmental gradients	
Composite sampling	Pool a number of samples together and only separate if the composite tests positive for some criteria.	Detection	Criteria for a positive test.	Rare

	Model-based stratification	Stratified sampling where strata are determined via a model	Prediction / Estimation	Auxiliary variates. Model for the stratification.	
	Quadrat sampling	Throw a quadrat at random and count within its boundary	Estimation		
	Recapture sampling	Take a sample, mark and release to the take a second sample and record number / proportion that were previously caught.	Estimation / Monitoring		Ability to release after initial capture
	Transect sampling	Take a sample along a transect of some variable / direction	Detection and limited estimation	Identification of appropriate transects.	Rare or elusive species
	Multiplicity sampling	Indirect sampling obtained from neighbourhood information.		Network of units.	Questionnaires (e.g. farm surveys) where units additionally report on neighbouring units.
	Patch-occupancy	Sample habitats and record presence/absence.	Estimation / prediction	Habitat knowledge	
Semi-random	Latin squares / hypercube (unaligned systematic)	Within a regular grid, perturb the sampling points.	Estimation and mapping		
	Snowballing / reputational sampling	A small number of units containing the rare species are used to form a network of other appropriate locations, from which a random sample can be taken.	Detection	Network of units	Rare
Geostatistical model	Kriging	Given a variogram model, sample points to produce a spatial map of the variable of interest.	Prediction	Variogram model	
	Variogram	Sample points to estimate the spatial dependence.	Estimation of spatial dependence		
Dynamic model	Population modelling	Construct model of population dynamics	Prediction / detection	Population model and auxiliary information such as host distribution.	
	Invasive species distribution modelling	Construct model of population dynamics and spread	Prediction / detection	Population and spread model. Host map and other data.	
	Risk-based sampling	Construct model of risk	Prediction / detection	Covariate information. Spatial model for risk	

	Epidemic modelling	Construct model of epidemic dynamics	Prediction / detection	Epidemic model. Host map and other data.
Predictive model	Distance based and map based model	Sample n hosts closest to the last detection	Prediction / detection	Host map
	Niche / habitat suitability models	Construct model of environmental niche	Prediction / detection	

B. HOSTS

TABLE 5: IDENTIFIED PSYLLID HOSTS, DATA FROM PSYL'LIST, NBN GATEWAY

Host Name	Associated psyllid vector
Carrot	<i>Trioza apicalis</i> <i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera trigonica</i> <i>Bactericera tremblayi</i>
Potato	<i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>
Tomato	<i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>
Cow Parsley	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Caraway	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Common Hogweed	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Parsnip	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Parsley	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Masterwort	<i>Trioza apicalis</i>
Aubergine	<i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>
Celery	<i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera trigonica</i> <i>Bactericera tremblayi</i>
Brassica spp	<i>Bactericera nigricornis</i> <i>Bactericera trigonica</i> <i>Bactericera tremblayi</i>
Ground Elder	<i>Trioza flavipennis</i>
Rock Samphire	<i>Bactericera crithmi</i>
Nettle	<i>Trioza urticae</i>
<i>Lycium</i> spp	<i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>
Broad-leaved dock	<i>Aphalara exilis</i> <i>Aphalara pauli</i> <i>Aphalara polygona</i> <i>Aphalara purpurascens</i>
<i>Rumex</i> spp	<i>Trioza rumicis</i>
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	<i>Bactericera tremblayi</i>
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	<i>Bactericera tremblayi</i>
<i>Capsicum</i> spp	<i>Bactericera cockerelli</i>

C. HOST MAPS

Maps of host locations can be obtained from a variety of sources.

For non-crop species, maps can be freely obtained from Online Atlas of the British and Irish flora http://www.brc.ac.uk/plantatlas/index.php?q=title_page. Shown below, are the presence/absence maps of wild carrot, and two caraway species.

Wild Carrot

Ref: <http://www.brc.ac.uk/plantatlas/index.php?q=plant/unmatched-species-name-382>

a) Caraway

b) Whorled caraway

http://www.brc.ac.uk/plantatlas/index.php?q=title_page

For a variety of crop species, low resolution maps are available under copyright from http://www.ukagriculture.com/crops/crops_regions_vegetable.cfm.

In addition, finer detail of crop density within Scotland will be maintained within agricultural records, such as the annual Economic Report on Scottish Agriculture.

Potato Crop locations in East Scotland, obtained from SASA (pers. comms)

Green – Ware crops, Pink – Seed potato crops.

D. PSYLLID DYNAMICS

Life Cycle – temporal population dynamics

For an overview of the biology and life cycle of psyllid species within Britain, see Sjölund et al. (2015). Hodkinson (2009) provides a complete overview of current knowledge in the literature regarding psyllid life cycle and behaviour. In order to construct dynamic models of psyllid behaviour, it is likely that more specific information relating to individual species is required, for example, the population growth rate. Due to the economic importance of Zebra chip disease, some research into this has been done for a selection of psyllid species, most notably *B. cockerelli* and *T. apicalis*. This information is summarised below from Haapalainen (2014) and Láska (2011) for *T. apicalis*:

- *T. apicalis* has one generation per year
- 100-1000 eggs hatching on host plant leaves with the emergence of adults after approximately 1 month depending on the season and climate, from which they then fly to either new host plants or to overwintering shelter plants (Haapalainen 2014).
- Total development time varied between glasshouse, lab and various field studies, (35-54 days). Time between the appearance of the first adult and first egg laid was found to be around 3 days. The

peak emergence (of adult) under field conditions was between 6am and 8am. Moreover, low temperatures were found to depress the propensity to fly (Láska, 2011).

- Many psyllids require flushes of young, rapidly growing plant tissue to breed, which can result in waves of psyllid outbreaks. Host plants may vary markedly in their suitability in successive years, for example species of *Rosaceae* exhibit biennial or irregular flowering patterns (Hodkinson, 2009).

Spatial Dynamics

There have been a number of studies into the dispersal patterns and spatial distribution of various psyllid species during the active summer period;

- Within the review by Hodkinson (2009), it was found that psyllids are highly effective at dispersing over both short and long distances. Moreover, psyllids with more than one generation per year can show differences in dispersal among the different generations, including some generations displaying longer distance dispersive behaviour or differences in the flight frequency.
- Prager et al. (2014), and references therein, investigated the spatial distribution of *B. cockerelli* within fields of tomato plants. It was found that the preferential location on plants seemed to depend on both the year and season. Moreover, they found fields of different crops to have different distributions and densities of *B. cockerelli*, but as with other psyllid species, there was a general preferential location at the field boundaries.
- In addition, Ramírez, et al. (2013) found the spatial distribution of the populations of eggs, nymphs and adults of *B. cockerelli* to be aggregated or clustered.
- Previous models have been developed incorporating psyllid dispersal dynamics and in particular, the dispersal of HLB by psyllid vectors has been modelled by repeated short jump distances characterised by a negative exponential dispersal (Parnell et al., 2014).

Migration and Overwintering habits

In addition to the active summer dispersal behaviour, various sources of information can be found regarding the overwintering migratory dynamics;

- *T. apicalis* can move up to 1km to overwintering shelter (Haapalainen, 2014).
- *T. apicalis* found in overwinter conifers up to 1km away from carrot fields (this was the maximum distance sampled) although most were found within 250m. Moreover, there was no obvious pattern between the prevailing wind and the direction which found most psyllids. Significantly more insects were found in groves compared to single stands of trees or indeed forests (Kristoffersen and Anderbrant 2007).
- *B. cockerelli* overwinters as source populations on *Lycium* and other wild solanaceae and then disperses with wind-assistance. In contrast, many temperate species overwinter on evergreen, usually conifers with several species (*C. melanoneura*, *C. affinis*, *B. albiventris* and *T. urticae*) recorded as overwintering on *Pinus* in northern England at around 13km away from nearest host. (Hodkinson, 2009).
- Láska (2011) found that the peak departure of adults from summer hosts was in middle of the day for *T. apicalis*.

E. PATHOGEN DYNAMICS

Sjölund et al. (2015) provides an overview of the epidemiology of Zebra chip disease and the causal agent, CaLsol. Here, we summarise various sources of information regarding the interactions between host-pathogen-vector for future reference of epidemic modelling;

- Munyaneza et al. (2014) investigated the bacteria infection rate in Norway of both the psyllid, *T. apicalis*, found to be 0.21-0.56, and of carrots, found to be 0.33-1.
- There has been evidence of CaLsol transmission to overwintering hosts (wild Lycium) of *B. cockerelli* (Lin and Gudmestad 2013).
- Level of CaLsol correlates with reduced fitness of psyllid, *B. cockerelli* (Nachappa et al., 2014)
- Evidence of transmission of pathogen in psyllid progeny (CaLsol found in eggs of *B. cockerelli*) (Haapalainen, 2014)
- *B. cockerelli* shows preference to infected potato plants then moved to uninfected plants, which were favoured for oviposition (Davis et al., 2012)
- *B. cockerelli*: adults more efficient than nymphs at transmitting pathogen to host. Inoculation period had little influence on disease incidence, severity or yield loss, indicating that once plants are exposed to an infected psyllid, the time spent exposed does not have an impact on the result. (Buchman et al., 2011).
- Between *T. apicalis* and carrots the inoculation access period was found to be as short as 3 days with 1-3 psyllids resulting in symptoms (Munyaneza et al., 2010).
- Seed potatoes infected with CaLsol generally do not germinate but, in rare cases may produce infected plants. Seed-borne infected plants are weak and short-lived and do not significantly contribute to disease spread (EPPO, 2013).
- Zebra chip infection has been shown to occur in spatial clusters (Henne et al. 2012).